

Leveraging Social and Psychological Capital to Improve SME Performance: Evidence from Knowledge Sharing Behavior in Indonesia

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ARTICLE INFO	ABSTRACT
<p>Published Online: 03 February 2026</p>	<p>Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) play a strategic role in regional economic development; however, their performance remains constrained by limited tangible resources and managerial capacity. In a knowledge-based economy, intangible resources such as social and psychological capital have become critical drivers of sustainable SME performance. This study aims to examine the effects of social capital and psychological capital on SME performance, with knowledge-sharing behavior as a mediating variable. The research was conducted among food and beverage SMEs fostered by the local government in Kediri. Using an explanatory research design, data were collected from 200 SME owners through structured questionnaires and analyzed using Structural Equation Modeling with the Partial Least Squares (SEM-PLS) approach. The results demonstrate that social capital and psychological capital have significant positive effects on knowledge sharing behavior and SME performance. Knowledge-sharing behavior is also found to have a direct positive effect on SME performance and partially mediates the relationships among social capital, psychological capital, and performance outcomes. These findings confirm that intangible capital contributes to SME performance not only directly but also indirectly through internal behavioral mechanisms related to knowledge exchange. This study contributes to the literature by integrating Social Exchange Theory, Positive Organizational Behavior, and the Knowledge-Based View of the Firm within the context of an SME in a developing economy. Practically, the findings highlight the importance of strengthening social networks, psychological resilience, and knowledge-sharing practices to enhance SME competitiveness and sustainability. From a policy perspective, the results provide empirical evidence to support SME development programs that emphasize the development of intangible capital alongside conventional financial and technical assistance.</p>
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<p>KEYWORDS: social capital; psychological capital; knowledge sharing behavior; SME performance.</p>	

1. INTRODUCTION

Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) play a strategic role in driving regional economic growth, job creation, and improving community welfare. In Indonesia, SMEs not only serve as the backbone of the national economy but also serve as the primary drivers of local economies, including in the Kediri region. However, SME performance still faces various structural and non-structural challenges, such as limited access to resources, low managerial capacity, and poor utilization of knowledge as a strategic organizational asset. (Mpofu & Sibindi, 2022).

In the context of increasingly dynamic, knowledge-based business competition, the competitiveness of SMEs is no longer solely determined by physical or

financial capital, but by intangible capital, particularly social and psychological capital. Social capital, reflected through trust, networks, and norms of reciprocity, plays a crucial role in facilitating information exchange and collaboration among business actors. Meanwhile, psychological capital, encompassing hope, self-efficacy, resilience, and optimism, serves as an individual's psychological foundation in navigating business uncertainty and fostering productive and adaptive work behavior. (World Economic Forum, 2022).

In an effort to boost economic progress, the government actively promotes the development of small and medium enterprises (SMEs). It supports the modernization of cooperatives to strengthen people's livelihoods and contribute to sustainable national growth and prosperity. The role of

SMEs in Indonesia's economic growth is significant, as evidenced by the fact that SMEs account for 99% of all business units. The role of SMEs in GDP has also reached 60.5%, and their employment share in the total workforce is 96.9%. (Coordinating Ministry for Economic Affairs, 2022)

Seeing the enormous potential role, SMEs have not been able to realize their business growth potential to the maximum. (Mpofo & Sibindi, 2022) Given the high failure rate of SMEs, it is important to examine the factors needed for their survival. The various challenges faced by small businesses can be outlined, including environmental, financial, and managerial aspects. (Jamie & Oliver, 2020) This indicates that in SMEs, the primary resources are generally held by the individual business owner, reflected in their abilities, knowledge, experience, and education level. Because there is no clear separation between owners and managers in SMEs, the business owner plays a key role in determining the company's direction and development. Therefore, the success or failure of an SME is heavily influenced by the owner's competence and expertise.

SMEs can respond more quickly and effectively to changing market needs by adapting their business strategies. Efforts to strengthen SME capacity through policy mobilization and investment aim to ensure the sector's active role in advancing the national economy and maintaining a balanced environmental ecosystem. This combination of strong networks, an adaptive mindset, and rapid information circulation enables SMEs to maneuver more nimbly than large companies in facing the dynamics of the business environment.

Indonesia's small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) play a significant role in supporting economic growth and creating jobs across the country. However, these businesses often face significant challenges in maintaining competitiveness, particularly during times of crisis. (Juniasih et al., 2019) In recent years, the importance of social capital has been increasingly recognized as a crucial factor in enhancing SME resilience and adaptability to changing economic conditions. (Sutrisno et al., 2024).

Social capital serves as a crucial external asset for SMEs, providing access to valuable resources through established networks and fostering trust among stakeholders. (Shan & Tian, 2022) These social connections can open doors to new markets, funding opportunities, and strategic partnerships, increasing a company's growth potential. However, recent research has presented mixed findings, suggesting that social capital does not always directly translate into improved performance. Having a broad network is not enough; success depends on entrepreneurs' ability to leverage these relationships effectively. Skills such as communication, negotiation, and strategic thinking are crucial for converting social capital into tangible benefits. (Purwati et al., 2021).

In times of crisis, small and medium-sized enterprises rely heavily on their leaders' psychological capital to navigate uncertainty and maintain resilience. Leaders with high psychological capital are more likely to pursue proactive investments, innovative solutions, and strategic growth, ultimately improving organizational performance. Conversely, leaders with low psychological capital tend to adopt defensive and risk-averse strategies that can hinder long-term sustainability and growth. (Julian et al., 2025) Other research also shows that social capital can contribute significantly to SME performance, both directly and through the mediation of innovation and knowledge. For example, trust and social networks have been shown to improve the performance of agribusiness SMEs in Bali. (Juniasih et al., 2019), strengthening the resilience of the batik business in Central Java. (Sutrisno et al., 2024).

Psychological capital significantly improves the performance, innovation, and resilience of Indonesian SMEs. (Fiernaningsih et al., 2024) By cultivating a positive mental attitude, self-confidence, hope, and optimism, these businesses are better prepared to adapt to changing market conditions and uncertainty. This mental strength enables businesses to compete effectively and sustain growth in a challenging economic environment. (Grözinger et al., 2023) Based on the identified problems, the objectives of this study are to examine the influence of social capital and psychological capital on knowledge sharing behavior in Kediri City SMEs, to examine the influence of social capital and psychological capital on the performance of Kediri City SMEs, to examine the influence of knowledge sharing behavior on the performance of Kediri City SMEs, and to examine whether knowledge sharing behavior mediates the influence of social capital and psychological capital on the performance of Kediri City SMEs.

This study makes a theoretical contribution by enriching the SME management literature by integrating Social Exchange Theory (SET), Positive Organizational Behavior, and the Knowledge-Based View of the Firm into a comprehensive conceptual model. Specifically, this study positions knowledge-sharing behavior as a mediating mechanism explaining how social capital and psychological capital translate into SME performance. These findings broaden the theoretical understanding of the role of intangible capital in the context of SMEs in developing countries, while addressing the inconsistency in previous research that often examines direct relationships without considering internal organizational processes.

From a practical perspective, this research provides strategic guidance for SMEs to improve business performance by strengthening social and psychological capital, thereby fostering a culture of knowledge sharing. The research findings can serve as a foundation for SME owners and managers to develop management practices that

emphasize trust, collaborative networks, and the strengthening of psychological factors such as self-confidence, optimism, and resilience.

Policy-wise, this research provides empirical evidence for local governments and relevant stakeholders in designing SME development programs that are more oriented toward strengthening intangible capital. The research findings serve as a foundation for formulating SME development policies that emphasize not only access to capital and technical training but also the development of business networks, learning communities, and psychological capacity-building programs for SME actors. In the context of Kediri, policies based on this research have the potential to increase the effectiveness of SME empowerment programs and encourage sustainable local economic growth.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

This research uses the Social Exchange Theory (SET) proposed by Homans (1958) and developed by Blau (1964). Social Exchange Theory is an approach that focuses on how individuals make decisions in social interactions by weighing benefits and costs. This theory argues that individuals engage in social relationships to gain benefits and avoid losses. The basic principle of this theory is similar to the concept in economics, where individuals seek to maximize the returns from their investments in social relationships. Social relationships are built on the exchange of resources, including knowledge, information, and even trust.

The theoretical concept of social exchange encompasses social relations between parties who interact due to material and non-material needs, such as support, trust, self-esteem, and prestige, as well as specific goals. Individuals often consider the presence or absence of punishment and rewards during the social exchange phase (Homans, 1958). This theory states that interpersonal interaction is a process in which parties exchange valuable resources. SET focuses on micro-level analysis, particularly the social reality between individuals (Umar, 2017).

The correlation between the variables studied using SET theory through social capital on SME performance is that social capital plays a fundamental role in helping SMEs access support, information, and valuable resources through building and maintaining strong connections. These relationships foster mutual trust and collaboration, offering various benefits consistent with the principles of Social Exchange Theory. Ultimately, these connections enhance SME growth potential, empowering entrepreneurs to thrive in a competitive marketplace.

2.1 Hypothesis Development

The application of psychological capital and social capital advantages and capabilities to the new generation of entrepreneurs helps obtain the resources

and information needed for entrepreneurship, encourages entrepreneurial success, and thereby improves entrepreneurial performance. (Wang et al., 2022) Psychological capital helps improve entrepreneurs' social and communication skills, thereby significantly enhancing their entrepreneurial performance. The importance of social capital in improving company performance, especially in small- and medium-sized industries, is demonstrated by the research of Ha & Nguyen (2020) and Nurkhin & Fikriyah (2022). Research findings show that social capital influences company performance. Organizations with substantial social capital are better equipped to gather resources that can improve business performance. (Hilmawati et al., 2023).

Another factor that influences company performance, especially in small and medium-sized industries, is psychological capital, as found in the research by Ezranta et al. (2023) and Winata (2024). Research shows that psychological capital positively influences company performance. Psychological capital positively predicts entrepreneurial success. This is because each element of psychological capital empowers entrepreneurs to overcome challenges as their businesses grow. (Baluku et al., 2016). From this explanation, the following hypothesis is formulated:

H1: Social Capital and Psychological Capital have a significant influence on the Knowledge Sharing Behavior of small and medium industrial businesses.

Social capital is the set of values embedded in social networks in relationships between individuals or groups within an organization. Nodes and ties are components of social networks, which serve as channels for connecting network members and promoting access to helpful information and financial ideas. (Bongomin et al., 2020) Psychological capital positively contributes to knowledge-sharing behavior. In addition, collective psychological capital, which is based on individual psychological capital, describes collective members' positive evaluations of the group environment and expectations for collective development and success, including the four dimensions of collective efficacy, hope, optimism, and resilience. (Goswami and Agrawal, 2022).

The importance of social capital in increasing knowledge-sharing behavior within organizations or groups is demonstrated by research by Hoang & Truong (2021) and Setini et al. (2021), which indicates that social capital positively influences knowledge-sharing behavior in SMEs. In addition to social capital, psychological capital also contributes to increased knowledge-sharing behavior in organizations. The studies by M. Chen et al. (2023) and Liu et al. (2023)

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show that psychological capital influences knowledge-sharing behavior in organizations. Based on this explanation, the following hypothesis is formulated:

H2: Social capital and psychological capital influence business performance in small and medium industries.

Knowledge sharing behavior occurs when people discuss and share their knowledge in ways that help everyone better understand, creating new understanding. Knowledge is shared between individuals and organizations to develop common goals for the organization to achieve a competitive advantage. (Laily and Ernawati, 2020) Knowledge-sharing behavior drives competitive advantage by reducing costs and improving performance. Learning processes for organizational growth can only occur when companies invest in explicit knowledge sharing for use, reuse, or renewal. (Ganguly et al., 2019) Utilizing knowledge sharing can be the key to improving business performance. This aligns with research from Armansyah et al. (2024) and Masduki et al. (2024), which shows that knowledge sharing positively influences a company's business performance. Based on this explanation, the following hypothesis is formulated:

H3: Knowledge Sharing Behavior significantly influences Business Performance in small and medium industries.

In essence, this social capital theory can encourage individuals to share their knowledge with

others. Various previous studies examining the influence of social capital and knowledge sharing on SME performance serve as the basis for this study's re-evaluation of both. (Nurkhin and Fikriyah, 2022) Psychological capital is a form of positive organizational behavior; it can be seen as the strength and capacity of positively oriented human resources. Psychological capital is an individual's measurable and exploitable positive mental abilities that can improve work performance. Knowledge sharing is a process that requires a specific mindset and a propensity to share, which in turn requires specific individual behaviors and attitudes within a particular organizational culture. Knowledge sharing is an unnatural behavior, as individuals hide it due to its importance and value, and because of how it affects the organization's values. (Hijawi et al., 2021).

Based on research by M. Chen et al. (2023) and Pentury (2023), social capital and psychological capital influence business performance through knowledge sharing. Knowledge-sharing behavior can act as a bridge or mediator in the relationship between social capital and company performance. Based on this explanation, the following hypothesis is formulated:

H4: Social capital and psychological capital have an influence on business performance in small and medium industries through knowledge-sharing behavior.

From this description, the research model is described as follows:

Picture 1. Conceptual Framework of Research

3. METHOD

3.1 Research Design

The research design used in this study is explanatory, examining causal relationships among variables through hypothesis testing. The goal of explanatory research is to discover the causes and reasons for a phenomenon by conducting a series of hypothesis tests.

3.2 Population and Sample

This study examines small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) in the food and beverage sector, specifically those registered with the Kediri City Department of Industry and Trade (Disperindag) as fostered. According to Disperindag data, in 2024, the number of SMEs under their guidance reached 9,827.

The sampling technique used was simple random sampling, a method of selecting samples from the population at random without regard to strata (levels). The sample size in this study was determined using the Slovin sampling technique with a 7 percent margin of error, yielding a sample size of 199.93.

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N e^2}$$

Where :

$$N = 9827$$

$$E = 0.07$$

$$n = \frac{9827}{1 + 9827 \times (0,07)^2}$$

$$n = 199,93$$

According to Ghozali & Latan (2015), the recommended sample size for Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) analysis ranges from 100 to 200. Ghozali stated that a minimum sample size of 100 is acceptable, but ideally between 100 and 200 is recommended to obtain valid and reliable results in SEM, especially when using the Maximum Likelihood (ML) estimation method. Therefore, the sample size used is 200.

3.3 Research Instruments

This research methodology uses a carefully structured questionnaire, designed with a comprehensive set of variable indicators, to systematically collect and analyze relevant data for the research, as shown in the following table:

Table 1. Variables, Indicators, Statements, and Sources

Variables	Indicator	Statement
Social Capital	Trust	Other UKM actors in my area can be trusted to work together. I feel safe sharing ideas and opinions with other business owners. SMEs in my area will help me if I face business obstacles.
	Social Network	I have a good working relationship with other business owners. My business often collaborates with other business groups or business partners in business activities. I can easily get help or information from fellow business owners.
	Norm	There is a culture of mutual assistance and cooperation among business owners Honesty is upheld in every transaction or collaboration among SMEs in my environment.
Psychological Capital	Confidence	confident in my business abilities, to pursue opportunities and manage a business I can face the challenges faced in running a business. I can overcome any obstacles or barriers that may occur.
	Optimism	The emergence of new opportunities in my business can increase business growth. Hard work will definitely help me achieve my business goals successfully I have a positive attitude towards change and innovation in managing my business.
	Hope	I remain optimistic and have confidence that the future of my business will be better. The hope of continued growth is always there when facing business problems.
	Resilience	When business conditions are difficult, I can handle the pressure. There is always an opportunity to learn and grow when facing failure.
Knowledge Sharing Behavior	Providing knowledge	I actively share knowledge about my business with other SMEs. I share my experiences with other SME players on success and failure in business management. When I gain new knowledge about SMEs, I am willing to share it with other business actors.

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	Knowledge gathering	My SME colleagues are happy to share their experiences about running a business with me. I am open to receiving information and knowledge regarding business development from UKM colleagues. I learned many new skills from discussions with other SMEs.
Entrepreneurial Performance	Financial	My business experiences an increase in sales volume every year My business experiences increasing profits every month. The business capital that I have is constantly increasing.
	Non-Financial	My business has experienced an increase in the number of employees Promote my products within the region and outside the region

3. 4 Data Analysis Techniques

The analysis technique uses Structural Equation Modeling (SEM). The SEM method is used to test research hypotheses by systematically analyzing the causal relationships between exogenous and endogenous variables. This method examines the interdependencies among variables, enabling researchers to understand complex patterns and validate theoretical models with greater precision and clarity.

4. RESULTS & DISCUSSION

4.1 Result

Profile of Small and Medium Enterprises: Kediri City, the third-largest city in East Java, had a population of approximately 292,768 in 2018. With an area of 67.2 square kilometers, the city is known for its rich cultural heritage and vibrant community life. The city is surrounded by Kediri Regency, which adds to its unique geographical and administrative significance. Kediri's strategic location and historical significance make it an important center in East

Java. Administratively, it is classified into three districts: Mojoroto District, Kota District, and Pesantren District.

4.2.1 Data Description

The respondent data collection process was conducted using an approach tailored to the characteristics of each SME in Kediri City. The Kediri City Government, through the Department of Trade and Industry, has fostered SMEs. Furthermore, based on Mayoral Regulation No. 4 of 2023, each sub-district has a "cool village" (kampung keren) designated as a "resort village." Respondents included the "jamu" (herbal medicine) village, the "tofu" (tofu) village, and the "soto" (soto) village. Kediri City also has Joint Business Groups (KUBE) in several sub-districts.

The respondents in this study were SMEs in Kediri City. The profile of the respondents in this study is described using descriptive statistics, including several characteristics, such as gender. A description of respondents by gender can be seen in Table 2:

Table 2. Number of Respondents Based on Gender

By Gender	Amount	Presentation
Man	71	35.5%
Woman	129	64.5%
Total	200	100%

Source: Processed primary data (2025)

Based on the research results, the majority of respondents were female (129, 64.5%), and 71 were male (35.5%). A description of the respondents by age can be seen in Table 3:

Table 3. Number of Respondents Based on Age

By Age	Amount	Presentation
20-30 Years	4	2%
31-40 Years	64	32%
41-50 Years	102	51%
Over 50 Years	30	15%
Total	200	100%

Source: Processed primary data (2025)

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Table 3 shows that the majority of SME owners are aged 41-50 years (102 respondents or 51%), followed by SME owners aged 31-40 years (64 respondents or 32%), then SME owners aged 50 years and above (30 respondents or 15%), and

finally SME owners aged 20-30 years (4 respondents or 2%). The description of respondents based on the length of business can be seen in Table 4 as follows:

Table 4. Number of Respondents Based on Length of Business

Length of Business	Amount	Presentation
1-2 Years	8	4%
3-5 Years	89	44.5%
Over 5 Years	103	51.5%
Total	200	100%

Source: Processed primary data (2025)

Based on the research results, the information obtained shows that the majority of respondents have been running their businesses for more than 5 years with a total of 103 respondents or 51.5%, then businesses that have been running for 3-5 years are 89 respondents or 44.5%, and

finally those who are still running their businesses for 1-2 years are 8 respondents or 4%. The description of respondents based on business owners joining business groups can be seen in Table 5:

Table 5. Number of Respondents Based on Business Group Membership

Information	Amount	Presentation
Joined	84	42%
Not Joined	116	58%
Total	200	100%

Source: processed primary data (2025)

Referring to Table 5, the characteristics of respondents who joined a business group indicate that 53 respondents, or 26.5% of business owners, joined a business group, while 147 respondents, or 73.5%, did not.

4.2.2 Validity and Reliability Test Results

The results of the analysis of the distribution of questionnaires to 176 respondents produced primary data that must be tested for validity and reliability before further analysis is carried out. proving that the 29 statement items tested for validity using the product-moment

correlation technique for all statement items proved that the calculated r value had exceeded the cut-off r table figure of 0.138. In addition, none of the resulting probability values exceeded the error rate (α) of 0.05. This proves that the respondents understood the 29 statement items or that the questionnaire instrument/items were deemed valid. This test was carried out to assess the consistency of respondents' answers. The technique for conducting reliability tests uses the Cronbach's Alpha formula.

Table 6. Results Reliability Test

No.	Research Variables	Number of items tested	Chronbach Alpha Value	r table	Results
1	Social Capital (X1)	8	0.917	> 0.138	reliable
2	Psychological Capital (X2)	10	0.926	> 0.138	reliable
3	Knowledge Sharing Behavior (Y1)	6	0.888	> 0.138	reliable
4	Business Performance (Y2)	5	0.905	> 0.138	reliable

4.2.3 Structural Model Test Results

This study uses two test models implemented in SmartPLS: the measurement

model, also known as the outer model, and the structural model, or inner model. Based on the Partial Least Squares estimation method, a Full

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Structural Model path diagram is obtained as shown in the following figure:

Picture 22. Structural Model

4.2.4 Convergent Validity Testing

Validity testing for reflective indicators uses the correlation between item scores and construct scores. Measurement with reflective

indicators shows changes in one indicator within a construct if other indicators within the exact construct change.

Table 7. Convergent Validity Test

Indicator	Knowledge Sharing Behavior (Y1)	Business Performance (Y2)	Social Capital (X1)	Psychological Capital (X2)
Trust			0.896	
Social Network			0.906	
Norm			0.921	
Confidence				0.876
Optimistic				0.870
Hope				0.867
Resilience				0.892
Providing Knowledge	0.946			
Knowledge Gathering	0.949			
Financial		0.951		
Non-Financial		0.947		

Referring to Table 7, all variables appear valid. This is because the loading factor value exceeds 0.60.(Hair et al., 2019). Because all loading factor values are above 0.06, each

indicator significantly contributes to explaining its respective research variable. In addition to loading factor values, the AVE value can be used to assess

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the validity of research data. Below are the results of the validity test using the AVE value.

Table 8. AVE Test Results

	<i>Average variance extracted(AVE)</i>
Social Capital (X1)	0.823
Psychological Capital (X2)	0.768
Knowledge Sharing Behavior (Y1)	0.898
Business Performance (Y2)	0.900

According to Table 8, all research variables appear valid. This is because the AVE value is above the threshold of 0.50.(Hair et al., 2019). For this reason, all manifest variables are said to meet the requirements of convergent validity.

4.2.5 Discriminant Validity

The measurement of discriminant validity to see the measurement of cross-loading factors with constructs and the comparison of AVE with the correlation of latent variables is shown below:

Table 9. Results: Cross-Loading Factor Test

	Social Capital (X1)	Psychological Capital (X2)	Knowledge Sharing Behavior (Y1)	Business Performance (Y2)
Trust	0.896			
Social Network	0.906			
Norm	0.921			
Confidence		0.876		
Optimism		0.870		
Hope		0.867		
Resilience		0.892		
Providing Knowledge			0.946	
Knowledge Gathering			0.949	
Financial				0.951
Non-Financial				0.947

Referring to Table 9, the cross-loading factor correlation values for each latent construct indicate which indicators are more suitable than

others. Thus, the indicators used in assessing the latent variables have met the requirements.

Table 10. Test ResultsFornell-Lacker

	Business Performance (Y2)	Psychological Capital (X2)	Social Capital (X1)	Knowledge Sharing Behavior (Y1)
Business Performance (Y2)	0.949			
Psychological Capital (X2)	0.829	0.876		
Social Capital (X1)	0.828	0.815	0.907	
Knowledge Sharing Behavior (Y1)	0.846	0.831	0.828	0.948

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Based on Table 10, this variable shows a higher correlation than the other variables, indicating that all included variables are valid and suitable for analysis.

4.2.6 Reliability Test

Comprehensive reliability testing to ensure the accuracy and consistency of results, and confirm that the data remains reliable across conditions and repetitions to ensure its overall consistency, accuracy, and credibility.

Table 11. Test Results Composite Reliability

	<i>Cronbach's alpha</i>	<i>Composite reliability</i>
Social Capital (X1)	0.893	0.933
Psychological Capital (X2)	0.899	0.930
Knowledge Sharing Behavior (Y1)	0.887	0.946
Business Performance (Y2)	0.889	0.947

According to the table, all constructs in the study appear reliable, as their Composite Reliability values exceed 0.70.(Hair et al., 2019).

4.2.7 Inner Model Evaluation

After testing the Outer Model criteria model, the next step is to test the Inner Model. The following are the R-Square (R²) values for the research constructs:

Table 22. Results of the Determination Coefficient Test

	<i>R-square</i>	<i>R-square adjusted</i>
Knowledge Sharing Behavior (Y1)	0.758	0.755
Business Performance (Y2)	0.789	0.785

The R-squared table shows how much the X variable explains the Y variable's variation in the research model. Based on the results above, the R-square for the Knowledge Sharing Behavior variable (Y1) is 0.758, indicating that the X variable can explain 75.8% of the variation in Y1. In comparison, the remaining 24.2% is explained by other factors outside the model. Meanwhile, the R-square value for the Business Performance variable (Y2) is 0.789, indicating that 78.9% of the variation in Business Performance is explained by

the model's variables, with the remaining 21.1% explained by other factors not studied.

The adjusted R-square for the knowledge-sharing behavior variable is 0.755, indicating a moderate level of goodness-of-fit. This also means that the independent variables can explain 75.5% of the variability in knowledge-sharing behavior. The adjusted R-square for the business performance variable is 0.785, indicating a moderate level of goodness-of-fit. This also means that the independent variables can explain 78.5% of the variability in business performance.

4.2.8 F Square Test

This test examines the relative influence of the independent latent variable on the dependent latent variable.

Table 13. F Square Test Results

Information	F-square
Knowledge Sharing behavior -> Business Performance	0.154
Psychological capital -> Knowledge Sharing Behavior	0.299
Psychological capital -> Business Performance	0.102
Social capital -> Knowledge Sharing Behavior	0.281
Social capital -> Business Performance	0.104

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Table 13 shows the F-squared values for the business performance variable of 0.154, 0.102, and 0.104. Therefore, it can be concluded that the independent variables influencing the business performance variable have a moderate influence.

The f-square value for the Knowledge Sharing Behavior variable is 0.299 and 0.281. Therefore, the variable influencing the Knowledge Sharing Behavior variable has a moderate effect.

4.2.9 Hypothesis Test Results

Table 14. Results of Hypothesis Test One

	<i>Original sample (O)</i>	<i>Sample mean (M)</i>	<i>Standard deviation (STDEV)</i>	<i>T statistics (O/STDEV)</i>	<i>P values</i>
Social Capital (X1) -> Knowledge Sharing Behavior (Y1)	0.450	0.451	0.094	4,781	0,000
Psychological Capital (X2) -> Knowledge Sharing Behavior (Y1)	0.464	0.464	0.087	5,356	0,000

Based on Table 14, the Social Capital variable (X1) has a significant effect on Knowledge Sharing Behavior (Y1), with a coefficient of 0.450, a t-statistic of 4.781, and a p-value of 0.000. The calculation results show that the t-statistic $4.781 > t\text{-table } 1.96$ and the p-value $0.000 < 0.05$. In conclusion, social capital has a significant positive effect on Knowledge Sharing Behavior.

Based on Table 14, Psychological Capital (X2) has a significant influence on Knowledge Sharing Behavior (Y1), with a coefficient of 0.464, a t-statistic of 5.356, and a p-value of 0.000. The calculation results show that the t statistic is $5.356 > t(1.96)$ and the p-value is $0.000 < 0.05$. In conclusion, psychological capital has a significant positive influence on Knowledge Sharing Behavior. Therefore, H1 in this study is accepted.

Table 15. Results of the Second Hypothesis Test

	<i>Original sample (O)</i>	<i>Sample mean (M)</i>	<i>Standard deviation (STDEV)</i>	<i>T statistics (O/STDEV)</i>	<i>P values</i>
Social Capital (X1) -> Business Performance (Y2)	0.289	0.276	0.103	2,795	0.005
Psychological Capital (X2) -> Business Performance (Y2)	0.289	0.295	0.099	2,932	0.004

Source: Processed primary data (2025)

Referring to Table 15, it appears that apl Capital (X1) has a direct effect on Business Performance (Y2) with a coefficient of 0.289, a t-statistic of 2.795, and a p-value of 0.005. The calculation results show that the t-statistic is $> t(1.96)$ and the p-value is < 0.05 . Therefore, the conclusion is that social capital has a positive and significant effect on business performance.

Performance (Y2), with a coefficient of 0.289, a t-statistic of 2.932, and a p-value of 0.004. The results of the calculation show that the t statistic is $2.932 > t\text{ table } (1.96)$ and the p-value is $0.004 < 0.05$. In conclusion, psychological capital has a significant positive effect on business performance. Therefore, H2 in this study is accepted.

Based on Table 15, Psychological Capital (X2) has a direct effect on Business

Table 16. Results of the Third Hypothesis Test

	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Standard deviation (STDEV)	T statistics ((O/STDEV))	P values
Knowledge Sharing Behavior (X1) -> Business Performance (Y2)	0.366	0.373	0.119	3,078	0.002

Source: Processed primary data (2025)

Referring to Table 16, the relationship between Knowledge Sharing Behavior (Y1) and Business Performance (Y2) has a coefficient of 0.366, a t-statistic of 3.078, and a p-value of 0.002. The results show that the t-statistic is 3.078 >

t(1.96) and the p-value is 0.002 < 0.05, indicating that Knowledge Sharing Behavior has a positive and significant influence on business performance. Thus, the third hypothesis in this study is declared accepted.

Table 17. Results of the Indirect Influence Test

	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Standard deviation (STDEV)	T statistics ((O/STDEV))	P values
Social Capital (X1) -> Knowledge Sharing Behavior (Y1) -> Business Performance (Y2)	0.165	0.173	0.076	2,171	0.030
Psychological Capital (X2) -> Knowledge Sharing Behavior (Y1) -> Business Performance (Y2)	0.170	0.170	0.054	3,173	0.002

Based on Table 17, the indirect effect of Social Capital (X1) on Business Performance (Y2) through Knowledge Sharing Behavior (Y1) has a coefficient of 0.165, a t-statistic of 2.171, and a p-value of 0.030. The calculation results show t statistic 2.171 > t table 1.96 and p value 0.030 < 0.05. In conclusion, social capital has a significant positive effect on business performance through knowledge-sharing behavior.

Performance (Y2) through Knowledge Sharing Behavior (Y1) has a coefficient of 0.170, a t-statistic of 3.173, and a p-value of 0.002. The calculation results show a t-statistic of 3.173 > t-table 1.96 and a p-value of 0.002 < 0.05. In conclusion, psychological capital has a significant positive effect on business performance through knowledge sharing. Therefore, H4 in this study is accepted.

Based on Table 23, the indirect effect of Psychological Capital (X2) on Business

Table 18. Results of the Total Influence Test

	Original Sample (O)	Sample Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T Statistics ((O/STDEV))	P Values
Psychological Capital (X2) -> Business Performance (Y2)	0.459	0.465	0.094	4,905	0,000
Psychological Capital (X2) -> Knowledge Sharing Behavior (Y1)	0.464	0.464	0.087	5,356	0,000
Social Capital (X1) -> Business Performance (Y2)	0.454	0.450	0.094	4,812	0,000

Social Capital (X1) -> Knowledge Sharing Behavior (Y1)	0.450	0.451	0.094	4,781	0,000
Knowledge Sharing Behavior (Y1) -> Business Performance (Y2)	0.366	0.373	0.119	3,078	0.002

Source: Processed Primary Data (2025)

4.2 Discussion

Knowledge-sharing behavior drives innovation, strengthens competitive advantage, and improves overall business performance. Knowledge sharing behavior directly improves the culture of innovation and business performance of SMEs, as well as building sustainable competitive advantage. This process also strengthens collaboration among SMEs, accelerates the adoption of new knowledge, and encourages the creation of innovative products or services (Arsawan et al., 2020). Knowledge-sharing behavior has been shown to strengthen business networks, accelerate information exchange, and enhance adaptability to market changes (Noya et al., 2025). Knowledge-sharing behavior is a key strategy that SMEs in Kediri must adopt to sustainably improve competitiveness and business performance.

Knowledge sharing behavior that contributes most to business performance is knowledge sharing. This indicator encompasses the process of knowledge distribution, both internally among employees and externally with business partners, communities, or customers. In the context of SMEs in Indonesia, knowledge sharing has been shown to strengthen innovation, accelerate adaptation to market changes, and increase business competitiveness (Pranowo et al., 2022). Entrepreneurial knowledge sharing in Kediri City involves external knowledge exchange with business partners, communities, or customers, expanding access to information, enriching knowledge resources, and opening opportunities for strategic collaboration. Knowledge sharing fosters a culture of innovation, strengthens organizational learning capabilities, and enhances adaptability to market dynamics (Arsawan et al., 2020).

For SMEs in Kediri City, building a culture of knowledge sharing is a crucial strategy for sustainably improving business performance. Knowledge-sharing practices can be implemented through internal training, discussion forums, collaboration with the business community, and the use of information technology to accelerate knowledge dissemination. These findings align with studies by M. Chen et al. (2023) and Rochma et al. (2025), which demonstrate that knowledge sharing behavior impacts business performance. When SMEs are

consciously and openly aware of new information and experiences from fellow entrepreneurs and the local government, they can transform social networks into economic value, ensuring that businesses consistently have an adequate information base for adaptation, innovation, and growth.

The influence of social capital on business performance through knowledge sharing behavior among SMEs in Kediri City is a crucial aspect in developing the business climate. SMEs possess a unique asset called social capital, which encompasses interpersonal trust, a broad network of contacts, and shared rules for working together. This helps businesses obtain information more quickly, develop products more easily, and find new customers or markets. This allows small businesses to grow more effectively, sell more, and use their resources more efficiently. Social capital plays a crucial role in encouraging knowledge sharing among SMEs, enabling them to thrive and adapt effectively in a dynamic market.

Within the scope of social exchange theory, social capital facilitates exchange because entrepreneurs trust other entrepreneurs, so they are not afraid of having their business ideas stolen due to the norm of reciprocity. This finding is relevant to studies by Aisjah et al. (2024) and Setini et al. (2021), which explain that knowledge-sharing behavior mediates the influence of social capital on business performance.

Psychological capital plays a significant role in shaping business performance through knowledge-sharing behavior. SMEs with substantial psychological capital play a crucial role in fostering a collaborative environment. By actively sharing knowledge and resources, these businesses enhance teamwork, encourage innovation, improve operational efficiency, and enhance overall business competitiveness. By maintaining a positive mindset, owners can motivate teamwork, enhance product quality, and improve overall performance. Therefore, mental resilience and a proactive attitude are crucial for sustainable growth and competitive advantage in a dynamic business landscape.

Psychological capital, within the scope of social exchange theory, is an internal asset that empowers individuals to engage in exchanges, empowering

entrepreneurs to have the confidence and conviction to share knowledge. This confidence in knowledge sharing provides collective benefits that flow back to their businesses. This aligns with studies by M. Chen et al. (2023) and Liu et al. (2023), which show that psychological capital influences business performance through knowledge-sharing behavior.

Knowledge sharing plays a crucial role in mediating social capital and psychological capital. Social capital serves as a crucial foundation for fostering collaborative interactions and building trust among business actors, which in turn encourages open knowledge sharing and collective growth. When individuals possess high levels of psychological capital, business actors are more likely to participate and contribute actively. This combination of social and psychological resources strengthens community bonds, enhances collaboration, and facilitates the smooth exchange of valuable knowledge within the business environment. These two factors are interconnected, resulting in positive business performance. Therefore, SMEs in Kediri City must focus on improving knowledge-sharing behavior to drive positive business performance.

Knowledge-sharing behavior is a concrete manifestation of social exchange theory, in which knowledge serves as a medium of exchange within social networks. When social capital provides a structure of relationships and trust, and psychological capital provides the mental readiness and courage to share, knowledge exchange occurs more intensively and with higher quality. Numerous studies have shown that knowledge sharing facilitated by social and psychological capital contributes to increased innovation, team effectiveness, and ultimately business performance.

The synergy between social capital, psychological capital, and knowledge-sharing behavior in improving SME performance can be explained through the lens of social exchange theory. Within this framework, these interactions are viewed as reciprocal processes based on norms and trust. SMEs are willing to distribute intangible resources, such as information and networks, if they perceive that the non-material benefits outweigh the costs. Research in the SME sector demonstrates that knowledge sharing acts as a key driver of absorptive capacity, innovation, and organizational performance. Specifically, knowledge distributed through social networks is the primary channel through which social capital influences operational performance. This confirms that the synergy between social and psychological capital triggers knowledge-sharing

behavior as a form of social exchange, which cumulatively impacts overall SME performance.

5. CONCLUSION

The results of this study demonstrate that higher levels of social and psychological capital can increase SMEs' willingness and ability to share knowledge effectively. Social capital, in the form of trust, social networks, and positive norms among individuals, fosters a sense of togetherness and openness in the process of transferring knowledge and experience. Psychological capital, on the other hand, strengthens individuals' readiness and willingness to share knowledge effectively. Among these variables, psychological capital is the dominant influence. This suggests that entrepreneurs with higher levels of psychological capital are more likely to achieve their business goals.

Research shows that entrepreneurs with social and psychological capital can improve business performance and sustainability in a competitive marketplace. Social capital provides resources and information that strengthen business productivity and effectiveness. Psychological capital, meanwhile, enhances an individual's capacity to manage and develop a business sustainably. With substantial social and psychological capital, entrepreneurs can increase innovation, build strong business relationships, and optimize resources, thereby significantly improving business performance.

Knowledge-sharing behavior among SMEs contributes to improved business performance. This activity enables the exchange of information, experiences, and practices among business actors, ultimately expanding the knowledge capacity of both organizations and individuals. With a culture of knowledge sharing, SMEs can develop product innovations and improve business process efficiency. Therefore, it can be argued that sharing behavior positively contributes to sustainable improvements in SME performance by strengthening organizational competence, efficiency, and competitiveness.

Individuals or groups with high social and psychological capital can improve business performance by actively sharing knowledge and ideas. Collaborative efforts among business actors foster innovation and creative solutions, enabling organizations to adapt and thrive. Through trust, motivation, and collective commitment, business actors work together effectively to achieve shared goals and drive overall success. Consistent with social exchange theory, social and psychological capital lower barriers to sharing, while knowledge-sharing behavior ensures that benefits are distributed throughout the organization, ultimately leading to improved performance.

Referring to the research findings and conclusions presented, the research contributions include: For the Government, it is necessary to design an SME development program that not only provides access to financial capital, but

also systematically builds the social and psychological capital of SME actors. Therefore, the government can strengthen SME community policies through business forums, business incubators, and shared service centers. Then, organize soft skills training to increase optimism, resilience, and self-confidence of entrepreneurs and provide a digital platform for knowledge sharing so that knowledge in social networks can be documented and transferred more widely.

For business actors, it is necessary to consciously invest time and resources to create and maintain networks (social capital) while strengthening the psychological capital of themselves and their employees by actively joining associations, communities, and business networks, and building trusting relationships with suppliers, customers, and fellow business actors to open up new knowledge flows and build an organizational culture that encourages knowledge sharing through regular meetings, mentoring, documentation of good practices, and a reward system for knowledge contributions.

For further researchers, they can deepen their understanding of the mechanism of influence of social capital and psychological capital on SME performance through several developments, namely including additional mediating and moderating variables such as knowledge absorption capacity, innovation, or digital transformation and expanding the research context to various sectors (manufacturing, services, agriculture, tourism) and different regions to compare the influence patterns.

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